

Existence of equations governing right triangle within the smallest acute angle of the right triangle

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Abstract

We prove that equations governing right triangle whose hypotenuse side and non-hypotenuse side (adjacent side) differ by any positive integer greater than zero within the smallest acute angle of the right triangle do exist.

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1 Introduction

In 1995 C.C. Chan and T.A. Peng proved the existence of infinitely many right triangles with integral sides in which lengths of two non-hypotenuse sides differ by 1 as shown in [2]. *But does the right triangle whose hypotenuse side and non-hypotenuse side (adjacent side) differ by any positive integer greater than zero within the smallest acute angle of the right triangle exist?* Let us call such triangle a *Mambosasa triangle*, also let the difference between hypotenuse side and non-hypotenuse side (adjacent side) be a *Mambosasa triangle order*. *But do equations governing Mambosasa triangle exist?* Answers to both questions will be shown in this paper.

2 Preliminaries

In this section we recall some definitions and basic notations of the Mambosasa triangle in **fig 1**.

Fig 1. Mambosasa Triangle (see definition 3)

Definition 1. Let b , c and m denote non-hypotenuse side (adjacent side), hypotenuse side and Mambosasa triangle order of the right triangle respectively such that

$$m = c - b$$

if and only if

$$0 < m \leq \infty.$$

Definition 2. Minimum angle is the smallest acute angle of the right triangle such that if (θ) is an acute angle then minimum angle is

$$0^\circ < \theta \leq 45^\circ$$

within the right triangle.

Definition 3. Mambosasa triangle is the right triangle whose hypotenuse side and non-hypotenuse side (adjacent side) differ by any positive integer greater than zero within the smallest acute angle of the right triangle.

3.0 Main Results

Theorem 3.1 If the difference between hypotenuse side and non-hypotenuse side (adjacent side) is the Mambosasa triangle order then

$$b = c - m \tag{1}$$

Proof. In fact, it follows that definition (1) satisfies Theorem (3.1) \square

Theorem 3.2 If θ satisfies definition (2) then the adjacent side (b) of the right triangle is

$$\frac{m \cos \theta}{1 - \cos \theta}$$

if and only if m satisfies definition (1).

Proof. Let us first recall that $\cos \theta = \frac{\text{adjacent}}{\text{Hypotenuse}}$ as in [1, 4]

$$\cos \theta = \frac{b}{c} \tag{2}$$

We substitute equation (1) into equation (2)

$$\cos \theta = \frac{b}{b + m}$$

$$(b + m) \times \cos\theta = \frac{b}{b + m} \times (b + m)$$

$$(b + m)\cos\theta = b$$

$$b\cos\theta + m\cos\theta = b$$

$$m\cos\theta = (b - b\cos\theta)$$

$$m\cos\theta = b(1 - \cos\theta)$$

we thus get

$$b = \frac{m\cos\theta}{1 - \cos\theta} \quad (3)$$

which proves Theorem 3.2. Now we show examples in **table 1**. \square

Theorem 3.3 *If B is the isosceles triangle base then*

$$B = 2(c - m)$$

if and only if m satisfies definition (1).

Fig 2. Isosceles triangle

Proof. Our proof starts with the observation that b is the adjacent side of the right triangle **QRS** in **fig 2**, then let

$$b + b = 2b. \quad (4)$$

Then let us substitute equation (1) into equation (4) which gives

$$2b = 2(c - m).$$

Then let

$$2b = B,$$

therefore

$$B = 2(c - m) \quad (5)$$

which completes the proof. \square

Theorem 3.4 *If hypotenuse side of the right triangle satisfies definition (1) then*

$$c = \frac{m}{1 - \cos\theta}$$

if and only if m satisfies definition (1) and θ satisfies definition (2).

Proof. Let $\cos\theta = \frac{\text{adjacent}}{\text{hypotenuse}}$ as in [1, 4]

$$\cos\theta = \frac{b}{c}$$

But

$$b = c - m \text{ (see equation 1)}$$

We thus get

$$\cos\theta = \frac{c - m}{c}$$

$$c \times \cos\theta = \frac{(c - m)}{c} \times c$$

$$c \cos\theta = c - m$$

$$c - c \cos\theta = m$$

$$c(1 - \cos\theta) = m$$

$$c = \frac{m}{1 - \cos\theta} \tag{6}$$

which completes the proof. \square

Theorem 3.5 *If h is the height of the right triangle, m is the Mamboasa triangle order and c is the hypotenuse side of the same right triangle then*

$$h^2 = 2mc - m^2$$

if and only if both h and m satisfy definition (1).

Proof. Let us first recall *Pythagoras theorem* ($h^2 + b^2 = c^2$) as in [1,3, 5]. (7)

Then we substitute equation (1) into equation (7)

we thus get

$$h^2 + (c - m)^2 = c^2$$

$$h^2 + (c - m)(c - m) = c^2$$

$$h^2 + (c^2 - cm - cm + m^2) = c^2$$

$$\begin{aligned}
h^2 + (c^2 - 2cm + m^2) &= c^2 \\
h^2 + c^2 - 2cm + m^2 &= c^2 \\
h^2 - 2cm + m^2 &= c^2 - c^2 \\
h^2 - 2cm + m^2 &= 0
\end{aligned}$$

then we obtain that

$$h^2 = 2cm - m^2 \quad (8)$$

therefore the proof is complete. \square

Theorem 3.6 *If both h and m satisfy definition (1) then*

$$h = \frac{m \sin \theta}{1 - \cos \theta}$$

if and only if θ satisfies definition (2)

Proof. Let $\sin \theta = \frac{\text{Opposite}}{\text{Adjacent}}$ as in [1, 4]

$$\sin \theta = \frac{h}{c} \quad (9)$$

then we substitute equation (6) into equation (9)

thus we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned}
h &= \frac{m}{1 - \cos \theta} \times \sin \theta \\
h &= \frac{m \sin \theta}{1 - \cos \theta}
\end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

which completes the proof of theorem 3.6 \square

Theorem 3.7 *If c is the hypotenuse side of the right triangle then area of the right triangle (A) is*

$$\frac{(c - m)\sqrt{2mc - m^2}}{2}$$

if and only if both m and c satisfy definition (1).

Proof. Let area of the right triangle be

$$\frac{\text{base}(b) \times \text{height}(h)}{2} \quad \text{as in [1].} \quad (11)$$

Then we substitute equation (1) and (8) into equation (11)

which gives

$$A = \frac{(c - m)\sqrt{2mc - m^2}}{2}$$

which completes the proof. \square

Theorem 3.8 *If θ satisfies definition (2) then area (A) of the right triangle is*

$$\frac{0.5m^2 \sin\theta \cos\theta}{\cos^2\theta - 2\cos\theta + 1}$$

if and only if m satisfies definition (1).

Proof. Let area = $\frac{\text{base} \times \text{height}}{2}$ as in [1] (12)

But

$$b = \frac{m \cos\theta}{1 - \cos\theta} \quad (\text{see equation 3})$$

and

$$(h) = \frac{m \sin\theta}{1 - \cos\theta} \quad (\text{see equation 10})$$

Then equation (12) become

$$\frac{\left(\frac{m \cos\theta}{1 - \cos\theta}\right) \times \left(\frac{m \sin\theta}{1 - \cos\theta}\right)}{2}$$

then we obtain that

$$A = \frac{0.5m^2 \sin\theta \cos\theta}{\cos^2\theta - 2\cos\theta + 1}$$

which completes the proof. \square

Theorem 3.9 *If P is the Perimeter of the right triangle, then*

$$P = (2c - m) + \sqrt{(2mc - m^2)}$$

if and only if both c and m satisfy definition(1)

Proof. Let perimeter (P) of the right triangle be $a + b + c$ as in [1]. (13)

Then let

$$h = \sqrt{2mc - m^2} \quad (\text{see equation 8})$$

and

$$b = c - m \quad (\text{see equation 1})$$

We substitute both equations (1 and 8) into equation (13).

Thus we obtain that

$$P = \sqrt{2mc - m^2} + (c - m) + c$$

$$P = (2c - m) + \sqrt{2mc - m^2}$$

which completes the proof. \square

Theorem 4.0 *If P is the Perimeter of the right triangle and m satisfies definition (1) then*

$$P = \frac{m(\sin\theta + \cos\theta + 1)}{1 - \cos\theta}$$

if and only if θ satisfies definition (2).

Proof. Let the perimeter of the right triangle be $h + b + c$ as in [1] (14)

But

$$h = \frac{m \sin\theta}{1 - \cos\theta} \quad (\text{see equation 10})$$

$$b = \frac{m \cos\theta}{1 - \cos\theta} \quad (\text{see equation 3})$$

and

$$c = \frac{m}{1 - \cos\theta} \quad (\text{see equation 6})$$

Then we obtain that

$$P = \left(\frac{m \cos\theta}{1 - \cos\theta} + \frac{m \cos\theta}{1 - \cos\theta} + \frac{m}{1 - \cos\theta} \right)$$

$$P = \frac{m(\sin\theta + \cos\theta + 1)}{1 - \cos\theta}$$

$$P = \frac{m(\sin\theta + \cos\theta + 1)}{1 - \cos\theta}$$

which completes the proof of Theorem 4.0, further examples are shown in **table 1**. \square

Table1. First seven Mambosasa triangle orders within a minimum angle of 36.87°.

Mambosasa Triangle order(m)	Minimum angle(θ)	Height(h) in centimetre	Hypotenuse(c) in centimetre	Base(b) in centimetre
1	36.87°	2.99999	4.99997	3.99997
2	36.87°	5.99998	9.999946	7.999946
3	36.87°	8.99997	14.99991	11.99991
4	36.87°	11.99996	19.99988	15.99988

5	36.87°	14.99995	24.99985	19.99985
6	36.87°	17.99994	29.99982	23.99982
7	36.87°	20.99993	34.99979	27.99979

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